

CIVIL ENGINEERING ASPECTS of ONSHORE WINDFARM DEVELOPMENTS

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SYNOPSIS

In the broad field of energy development, there are two overwhelming pressures now coming to bear on the Irish economy. One is pressure from the Kyoto Protocol to limit greenhouse gas emissions, the other our worsening reliance on imported fuels to meet our growing energy needs. These pressures are creating an urgent requirement for Ireland to *accelerate the development of renewable resources and in particular wind energy*. The most favourable locations for windfarms, in terms of wind frequency and speed, are often in unfavourable locations in terms of access and ground conditions. This paper addresses the civil engineering aspects of *windfarm developments, drawing on experience gained by Aertech, a division of ESB International, in the planning and construction of several windfarms around the country. The paper also presents the background against which a major upsurge in wind energy projects in Ireland is anticipated.*

1 Introduction

1.1 Recent Progress in Wind Energy Development

For three millennia man has utilised the power of wind for development and enhancement of living and, over the last three decades in particular, wind technology has evolved into a highly developed and increasingly competitive form of energy. This dramatic advancement in technology and efficiency is seen in Table 1, which shows the European Wind Energy Association's (EWEA) estimates of 1991 and 1996 for installed capacity in the year 2000. The initial estimates of 4000MW, made in 1991 and subsequently revised in 1996 to an estimate of 8000MW, have proven well short of the figure actually achieved which was 12,800MW. The EWEA has consequently revised its

1250MW for the year 2010. In a further boost to practitioners in the wind power business, in September of 2001 the European Parliament recognised the valuable production of electricity from renewable energy resources in the internal electricity market and introduced a landmark Directive 2001/ 77/EC for the wind energy industry. This Directive sets out a clear policy framework to encourage the increased use of wind power in the EU countries and provides important guarantees for investors and developers in wind energy projects. National Governments are now free to decide how they want to promote wind power. The Irish Wind Energy Association (IWEA) is seeking to influence this development through the AER programmes and, in conjunction with tax incentive measures, to achieve a 13%

applications for foreshore leases to the Minister for the Marine. In a historic signing and defining milestone in the development of offshore wind parks, the Minister for the Marine granted the first of these foreshore leases on 11 January 2002 to the green energy company, *airtricity*.

2 Stages in Development of a Windfarm

The development of a windfarm from initial conception to commercial operation will generally include the following phases:

- Site selection
- Feasibility Study
- Project assessment
- Planning application and Construction Licence
- Site Investigation and Detailed design
- Construction
- Commercial Operation (and decommissioning at the end of useful life)

Site selection is the first phase in any wind generation development and serves to identify suitable sites and define any technical, commercial and environmental constraints to ensure suitable projects are pursued in the most appropriate fashion. The feasibility of the selected site is examined in this phase. This will include on site wind monitoring, an economic assessment to establish the commercial viability, a scoping exercise to identify specific environmental constraints and an assessment of planning constraints.

Implementation of the project assessment phase will only follow if the studies in the earlier phases indicate that the windfarm

Table 1 European Wind Energy Association Estimates

Year 1991 estimates	Year 1996 estimates	Years	Year 2000 revised estimates	
4,000MW	4,000MW	2000	12,800	Actual
11,500MW	20,000MW	2005	30,000	2,500 offshore
25,000MW	40,000MW	2010	60,000	5,000 offshore
N/A	100,000MW	2015	150,000	50,000 offshore

estimates in 2000. Over the next eight years to 2010 this increased interest and activity is expected to see a five-fold increase in installed capacity to 60,000MW, of which 5000MW is expected to be generated in off shore windparks.

Wind power is now close to achieving a production price per kilowatt-hour that makes it a viable alternative to conventional energy production. The large modern windfarm on a good exposed site is able to compete with new coal fired plants, is cheaper than nuclear plants and is now close in production price to that of the modern gas fired plants.

The installed capacity in Ireland, to date, is 5MW, less than 1% of that in Europe. This is generated from 21 windfarms ranging in size from 1.2MW in Leitrim to 15.18MW in Kerry with an average size wind farm of 5.94MW. Northern Ireland has a further 9 wind farms with an installed capacity of 41MW.

Recognising our responsibilities under the Kyoto Protocol to reduce the alarming effect of the increase in green-house gas emissions, the Government has put in place a series of initiatives designed to encourage the installation of renewable energy projects in recent years. The Alternative Energy Requirement (AER) programmes together with European Thermic and Fifth Framework programmes have stimulated the Irish wind industry and the revised Irish target for year 2005 is 500 MW increasing to

indicative target level, in accordance with the Directive, of renewable energy contribution in the production of electricity by the year 2010.

1.2 Windfarm Schemes in the Planning Stages in Ireland

Local Authority planning offices in many counties have in recent months been busily engaged with planning applications for wind farms, in anticipation of inclusion in the current Government scheme for the AER5 competition. Under this scheme a successful

Table 2 Windfarms in the Planning Process

Onshore	No of counties	No of windfarms	Installation MW
Full planning permissions	18	46	436
Planning permission under appeal to ABP	11	17	106
Planning permission refused and under appeal to ABP	5	8	78
Planning Applications under examination by Local Authorities	8	20	740*
Onshore			
Applications for Foreshore Lease Licence	2	2	520‡

*Includes the Bord na Mona-ESB application for 320MW in Co. Mayo ‡Includes the foreshore lease granted for the 500MW Arklow Bank in Co. Wicklow

applicant would be guaranteed a purchase price level for 15 years for the energy generated from his project. The level of activity is seen from the statistics in Table 2 which shows there are currently permissions in 18 counties for 46 windfarms with an installed capacity of 436MW and a further 45 projects with a potential capacity of 924 MW in the planning process. In addition to this range of activities, developers of 520 MW of offshore wind parks have made

project is commercially and environmentally viable. Technical and commercial considerations are reappraised in this phase and the selection of the most appropriate wind turbine generator for the site is examined. An environmental impact statement and report is prepared and consultation undertaken with local authorities and communities in this phase.

The developer and his stakeholders having been appraised of the detailed technical,

commercial and environmental assessments and the suitability of the selected site may then submit a planning application to the Local Authority. The authority may wish to regulate the construction and operation of the development by means of planning conditions and obligations and the implication of these conditions for the development may require further detailed assessment on the viability of the project. A further prerequisite to construction is that permission be obtained for the connections to the national electricity network and a construction licence be obtained from the Commission for Electricity Regulations (CER).

When the viability of the project is confirmed and the various permissions and licences are in place, expenditure on construction-related activities can commence with the site investigation stage.

2.1 Site Investigation

The most favourable locations for wind-farms, in terms of wind frequency and speed, are often in unfavourable locations in terms of access and ground conditions. With a typical spacing of wind turbines of the order of 200m, windfarms can cover large areas. A farm with 12 turbines, for example, can require up to 5km of interconnecting access roads to facilitate construction and subsequent maintenance. It is clear, therefore, that uncertainties in the potential variation in ground conditions across a site represent a substantial risk in the development of a wind farm.

This risk can be mitigated by a carefully planned site investigation. The scope of the investigation may encompass the following:

- Determination of ground and groundwater conditions at the individual turbine locations to provide sufficient data for foundation design
- Determination of nature of ground

conditions along access road routes with a view to designing economic road construction

- If rock outcrops at the site appear promising, investigate the suitability of the rock body for development of a quarry to serve the needs of access road construction. Sourcing suitable road making materials on site in this manner significantly reduces construction costs as well as the impact of the development on the general public along the haulage routes to site.
- Determination of adequacy of existing public roads on the approach to the site to assess whether any road strengthening or widening at bends is necessary to accommodate heavy and long construction loads.

Experience on the Culligh, Co. Donegal and Comeen, Co. Cavan wind farm projects, where Aertech Ltd provided turnkey contracting services to the developer, *airtricity*, has concluded that a two-stage investigation is most appropriate. Both sites are on elevated ground with a covering of blanket bog. The stages of the investigations are indicated in Table 3 below.

The initial phase of the investigation

Table 3 Site-Investigation Stages

Investigation stage	Techniques	Conclusions
First Stage	Dynamic Probing Trialpitting	Peat thickness, tentative estimation of founding depth for turbines, groundwater conditions
Second Stage	Cable Percussion boring Rotary Coring and laboratory testing	Confirmation of founding depth for turbines, groundwater conditions

involved dynamic probing at 50m intervals along the access routes and at turbine locations. Dynamic probing using light-weight equipment provides a low cost initial reconnaissance picture giving an indication of peat depths across the sites and strength/density of the material below the peat. This was supplemented in the initial

stage of the investigation by trialpitting at the turbine locations. The initial stage of the investigations provided grounds for slight relocation of planned turbine positions and re-orientation of road alignments to locations with more favourable ground conditions. The second stage of the investigations was planned on the basis of the results of the first stage and involved deeper investigation at selected locations using cable percussion and rotary coring techniques, together with rock breaking and crushing trials (at Culligh).

The investigations at Comeen and Culligh revealed the general ground profiles indicated in Table 4.

2.2 Access road design

On elevated sites, planners generally prefer road alignments running along contour lines, which reduces their visual impact. Access roads can represent 50% of the cost of civil works on a wind farm site and economies identified at the design stage can significantly influence the final cost. Road widths of 4.5 to 5.0 metres are required depending on the turbine size being erected. At Culligh, where peat depths varied between 0.5m and 4m, two forms of road design were adopted:

- "Floating" Roads, founded directly on the peat surface
 - Roads founded on the till below the peat
- Where the depth of peat exceeded 2m, peat excavation to provide a formation level on the till below could have presented problems locally in terms of drainage and also resulted in high stone costs to achieve desired vertical alignments. In this scenario roads were "floated" by laying a high-strength geogrid directly on the undisturbed peat surface and overlaying with 300-600mm of site-won crushed Schist. The geogrid has the effect of providing high tensile strength across the plane of formation level, thereby resisting shear failure below wheel loads. Where the depth of peat was less than 2m, the peat was generally removed to permit formation directly on the underlying till. Rock breakers and a rock crusher on site were well capable of producing stone to the specification which required a maximum particle size of 200mm, a fines content not exceeding 10%, a uniformity coefficient (D60/D10) greater than 5 and a 10% Fines

FIGURE 1 Stage 2 Site investigation at Kingsmountain

FIGURE 2 Road cross-sections at Culligh

value in excess of 75kN. The specification for the final levelling course on the road network, not completed until all concrete and turbine installation works have been

on some sites where the floating technique is used have proved costly and time consuming. Clearly great care must be taken when adopting a form of access road

FIGURE 3 Typical wind turbine foundation at Culligh

concluded, varied the requirement for maximum particle size to 50mm. The road cross-sections adopted at Culligh are shown on Figure 2.

The experience with floating roads at Culligh has been very favourable with no evidence of pavement distress or significant settlement either during the construction stage or to date, now almost two years after construction. Significant settlement has, however, occurred under floating roads on some sites and crane operators have refused to make their plant available for servicing the turbines. Remedial measures undertaken

construction on a site underlain by soft soils. At Culligh, the fibrous nature of the near surface peat clearly provides a reinforcing effect that enhances the effect of the geogrid.

Table 4 Ground profiles at Culligh and Corneen

Ground Stratigraphy	
Culligh (site elevation 275m to 365m)	Corneen (site elevation 320m)
Soft very fibrous PEAT..... to max depth 0.3m	Soft fibrous PEAT..... to max depth 2m
Soft amorphous PEAT..... to max. depth 4m	Soft to firm sandy SILT with cobbles (Glacial Till)..... max. thickness 2 m
Firm to stiff sandy SILT with cobbles and boulders (Glacial Till)..... max. thickness 2m	Bedrock (LIMESTONE and SANDSTONE)..... between 1.7m and 3.7m below original ground level
Bedrock (SCHIST)..... between 0m (outcropping) and 4m below original ground level	

Amorphous peat is unlikely to possess this reinforcing characteristic and the use of floating roads should be treated with great caution on Amorphous peat sites.

2.3 Turbine Foundation design

There are differing approaches to foundation design, depending on the code of practice adopted. To date in Ireland, the majority of turbines erected are from Danish and German suppliers and design checks have generally followed these countries' codes with site specific inputs relating to soil parameters and wind speeds. With the advent of Eurocode 7 (Geotechnical Design), which is expected to attain full European Standard status (EN) in 2003, it is now becoming more appropriate to design wind turbine foundations in accordance with EC7. A comparison of the requirements of German and Danish foundation design code requirements with those of Eurocode produce interesting results in terms of the foundation size required for a given site. The primary differences are outlined in Table 5.

Using these factors with a given characteristic wind load, base size variations of up to 30% would be required for given ground conditions, depending on the code adopted. Stability considerations rather than bearing stress generally govern the foundation size required for a wind turbine. When stability checks are satisfied and if ground conditions within the upper 4m are adequate, a spread foundation of sizes varying from 9.0 x 9.0 m and 1m thick for turbines in the 700-900kW range to 16x16m and 1.5m thick for those in the 250 kW range are adopted. Applied bearing stresses in the range 150kN/m² to 250kN/m² generally apply under these spread foundations. The effects of a high groundwater table at a turbine location reduces the effective weight of the foundation and this must be compensated for by increasing the base size accordingly. On this basis, the results of the site investigation, in terms of characterisation of ground water table is very important. Figure 3 shows a typical foundation adopted on the Culligh project.

bearing stratum depends on the nature of the ground conditions. Uniform soils with a high silt or fine sand content, in conditions of high groundwater table, can liquefy under cyclic loading. The site investigation works should therefore include particle size distribution assessments of the soils at the proposed founding level.

When adequate ground bearing characteristics are not available within the upper 4–5m, the cost and potential difficulty of excavating for a spread foundation can become excessive. In these circumstances a piled foundation is generally considered. A multiple raked pile arrangement is usually adopted under a wide pile cap. If tension capacity can be achieved in the piles, either in shaft friction or by under-reaming at the toe, economies can be achieved in the pile cap construction requirements.

The reinforcement required in a spread foundation is governed by bearing pressures under the base and, in addition, by punching shear and dynamic load requirements. Reinforcement quantities vary from 7 to 20 tonnes depending on base being constructed.

2.4 Turbine Structure Design and Safety Requirements

The main structural components of a wind turbine are:

- i) **Tower** – a structural steel hollow section formed from connected modular lengths
- ii) **Nacelle** – a glass-reinforced plastic (GRP) covered steel frame at the top of the tower which houses the gearbox and generator
- iii) **Rotor blades** – formed from GRP

A typical arrangement of a single wind turbine is shown on Figure 4, and typical turbine dimensions and operating parameters in Table 6.

Wind turbines are generally designed in accordance with the recommendations of IEC 61400-1 produced by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). The IEC is the international standards and conformity assessment body for all fields of electro-technology. Documents produced by the IEC have the form of recommendations for international use and are published in the form of standards. The IEC does not provide any marking or certification procedure for an installation; such service is provided by Germanischer Lloyd or similar proving authority.

The wind conditions for the site are assessed from monitoring measurements made at the site, any long term records that exist and from information from local meteorological stations. IEC 61400-1 states that *the monitoring period shall be sufficient to*

Code of Practice	Features of Code		
	Ultimate Limit State Partial Factor on wind load, γ_f	Ultimate Limit State Partial Factor on foundation soil strength, $\gamma_{fnd} - \gamma_c$	Other Specific Requirements
Denmark	1.3	$\gamma_{fnd} - 1.3$ $\gamma_c - 2.0$	If tension under the base exists, further design check must be carried out to ensure that shear failure under the base does not occur
Germany	1.5	$\gamma_{fnd} - 1.3$ $\gamma_c - 1.3$	Tension not allowed under the base under normal operating conditions
Eurocode 7 (CASI, B generally governs foundation size)	1.5	$\gamma_{fnd} - 1.0$ $\gamma_c - 1.0$	When reaction is outside the middle third, i.e. tension under the base, the foundation width must be increased by 0.2m in both directions

obtain a minimum of six months of reliable data. Where seasonal variations contribute significantly to the wind conditions the monitoring period shall include these

IEC 61400 requires that a structural dynamics model should be used to obtain design loads. This is normally done by the wind turbine manufacturer where the wind

FIGURE 4 Typical wind-turbine system

The mechanical components of the drive train are housed in the nacelle (see FIGURE 5)

effects. In this country, the on-site monitoring period is normally a minimum of one year.

IEC 61400-1 classifies wind-turbine generator systems in terms of characteristic values of (i) wind speed values – wind speed with mean return period of 50 years (v_{ref}) and annual average wind speed (v_{ave}) – (both 10 min. mean values at hub height) and (ii) wind turbulence.

The wind turbine system should be designed to withstand the wind conditions defined by the WTGS class (see Table 7).

IEC 61400-1: Wind Turbine Generator Systems – Part 1 Safety Requirements specifies requirements for the safety of Wind Turbine Generator Systems (WTGS) including design, installation, maintenance and operation. Clauses 5, 6 and 7 deal with design philosophy, determination of loads and specification of load combinations for structural design.

FIGURE 5 General arrangement of components within the nacelle

turbine generator system is represented by a model including the tower and the foundation. Loads/stresses are obtained as time series for all critical points of the WTGS. All relevant combination of external conditions and wind turbine operational modes are required to be analysed; external conditions include environmental (wind and other), electrical and ground conditions.

Table 6 Main dimensions of typical turbines

Typical Wind Turbines – General Parameters

	Up to 900kW	900 kW - 1500 kW	> 1500kW
Rotor Diameter (m)	43-55	60-77	70-80
Rotor Revs (rpm)	15-28	10-20	10-27
Hub Height (m)	40-70	45-85	60-100
Cut in Wind Speed* (m/sec)	3-4	3-4	3-4
Nominal Output Wind Speed* (m/sec)	13-15	12-15	12-15
Cut out Wind Speed* (m/sec)	25	25	25

* At hub height

The blades rotate and commence generating power at wind speed of between 3m/s and 4m/s (known as *cut-in wind speed*). The power generated increases with wind speed and the nominal output rating of the turbine is reached between 12m/s and 15m/s. This is illustrated on the typical characteristic power curve for a turbine generator given in Figure 6.

In Clause 7.4 of IEC 61400-1 it is stated that *as a minimum the design load cases in Table 2 should be considered*. Load combinations for design situations (i) Power Production (ii) Power Production plus occurrence of fault (iii) Start-up (iv) Normal shut-down (v) Emergency shut-down (vi) Parked (vii) Parked and fault conditions, are given. The load combinations include the wind condition to be considered, the analysis check (i.e. ultimate or fatigue) to be carried out and the applicable safety factor category (see Table 8). The applicable partial safety categories are either Normal (normal and extreme) or Abnormal and the partial safety factors values γ_f for loads are given in Table 9. Partial safety factors for materials are given in terms of $\gamma_m = 1.1$ and γ_c for which values are given depending on the consequence of failure, the confidence limit

for the strength parameter and the design code.

IEC61400-1 states that for the determination of the structural integrity of elements of WTGS national or international design

codes for the relevant material may be employed. However, it is stated that *it shall be ensured that the resulting safety level is not less than the intended safety level in this standard*.

Foundations for wind turbines are subjected to moments, torques, shears and vertical loads transferred from the turbine tower (See Fig. 7). Typical foundation loads are given in Table 10.

2.5 Construction programme for windfarm

The successful conclusion of a windfarm project requires careful project management to ensure a smooth interface between the civil, electrical and turbine erection disciplines. Table 11 shows a typical construction schedule for a 10MW installation of wind turbines in the medium 600–900kW range.

2.6 Quality control on site

In advance of construction the capability of

FIGURE 6 Typical power curve of wind turbine

Table 7 Part-copy of Table 1 IEC 61400-1

WTGS Class	I	II	III	IV	S
V_{ref} (m/s)	50.0	42.5	37.5	30.0	Special Design and Offshore
V_{ovc} (m/s)	10.0	8.5	7.5	6.0	

*Subclassification within each category occurs dependent on turbulence characteristics.

Table 8 (Part-copy of Table 1 IEC 61400-1)

Design Situation	DLC	Wind Condition*	Other Conditions	Type of analysis	Partial Safety Factors
1) Power Production	1.1	NTM $V_{hub} = V_r$ or V_{out}		U	N
	1.2	NTM $V_{in} < V_{hub} < V_{out}$		F	+
	1.3	ECD $V_{hub} = V_r$		U	N
	1.4	NWP $V_{hub} = V_r$ or V_{out}	External Electrical fault	U	N
	1.5	EOG _r $V_{hub} = V_r$ or V_{out}	Loss of electrical connection	U	N
	1.6	EOG ₅₀ $V_{hub} = V_r$ or V_{out}		U	N
	1.7	EWS $V_{hub} = V_r$ or V_{out}		U	N
	1.8	EOG ₅₀ $V_{hub} = V_r$ or V_{out}		U	N
	1.9	ECG $V_{hub} = V_r$		U	N
6) Parked (standing still or idling)	6.1	EWM $V_{hub} = V_{c50}$	Possible loss of electrical power network.	U	N
	6.2	NTM $V_{hub} < 0.7 V_{ref}$		F	+

* If no cut-out wind speed V_{out} is defined, the value of V_{ref} should be used.
 + For fatigue failure $\gamma_f = 1.0$ (Note: Part copy of Table 2 IEC 61400-1)

the local concrete suppliers must be assessed to determine and ensure the supply of quality assured concrete for base construction. The substantial concrete volumes in spread foundations require careful pour planning to reduce the potential impact of cracking arising from thermal gradients across the concrete as it sets. It has always been ESBI concreting practice to complete a pour in one continuous operation, significant experience having been gained with very large pours during the construction of recent major power stations (pours of 1600m³). However, due to access difficulties and the logistics of pouring bases of 280m³ of concrete in remote locations on hillsides, consideration is being given to completing these in two equal pours with shear keys included as necessary. It is preferable, if time and weather constraints are not an issue, to complete the construction of all the bases on a windfarm in advance of turbine installation. A suitably selected concrete mix design with additional cement

Table 9 Copy of Table 3 IEC 61400-1

Source of Loading	Unfavourable Loads			Favourable Loads All Design Situations
	Type of design situation (See Table 2)			
	Normal and Extreme	Abnormal	Transport and Erection	
Aerodynamic	1.35	1.1	1.5	0.9
Operational	1.35	1.1	1.5	0.9
Gravity	1.1/1.35*	1.1	1.25	0.9
Other inertia	1.25	1.1	1.3	0.9

content will achieve an early strength and will allow erection of the turbine after 14 days curing rather than the usual 21 days.

FIGURE 7 Loading regime on wind turbine foundation

erected to the hub that has been coupled to the shaft and fixed in the nacelle previously raised. Whilst the tower bottom unit having being erected may be left overnight or at weekends, the complete tower cannot be left standing without the nacelle on top as, unless other precautions are taken, the tower and holding down bolts will be damaged due to unacceptable oscillations of the tower in high winds.

2.7 Transportation of Turbines to site
Considering the lengths of the blades to be transported special precautions have to be taken. Local authority and local garda/police traffic permits are required and specialist heavy/long load transportation companies

Table 10 Typical wind-turbine foundation loads

Typical loads applied to foundations (at the base of the tower) are as shown on Table 10 below:

Loadcase	F_x (kN)	F_y (kN)	M_x (kNm)	M_y (kNm)	Load Factor γ_1
1.1 (f)	2,000	570	510	31,000	1.35
6.1(b)	1,950	600	900	37,000	1.35

Erection of the turbine necessarily includes mobilisation of heavy cranes and large-scale delivery trucks for long and wide loads. At Corneen a 500 tonne main crane was used for erection with a 180 tonne tail crane. This craneage requirement dictated

employed. To gauge the extent of this operation, it should be noted that the normal long load in daily use on our roads is 17m whereas the blades of the 1500kW unit delivered last year had an overall length of 39m and for the 2500 kW units this will

Table 11 Construction schedule for typical 10MW windfarm

Activity	Duration (Weeks)
Site development	4*
Road construction	10
Base construction	7
Turbine installation	5
Electrical installation	6
Commissioning	4

*indicates total duration of activities in weeks

that 700m² of purpose-built hardstanding area was required for each turbine. Typical heavy-lift requirement details are shown in Table 12 that identifies to various items of plant and weights to be raised. In reasonable weather conditions, two days should be allowed for erection of the 700-900kW range turbines and five days allowed for those of 2500kW. The sequence of erection commences with the tower sections followed by the nacelle and then the hub with blades attached on the 700kW to 1500kW units – it is possible to carry out this work in wind speeds up to 14m/sec – 26 knots. For the 2500kW range, individual components are lifted and assembled in the nacelle, also blades may be individually

increase to 44m. In line with this detailed surveys have to be undertaken on selected

FIGURE 8 Foundation construction at Corneen
routes especially those on the minor roads adjacent to site. Road realignments and pavement strengthening is usually required and in one case a temporary Bailey bridge was erected to ensure delivery to schedule.

2.8 Electrical connection and installation

In advance of any construction on site, a construction licence has to be procured from the Commission for Electricity Regulation. Following a successful Planning Application a grid connection planning consent has to be achieved for supplies at 38kV or higher. Below this level agreement on wayleaves has to be obtained locally from those through whose lands the overhead line is constructed. One of the key items in the electrical installation programme is the procurement of the grid transformer. As this has a long lead for manufacture, test and delivery to site, ordering this item has to be put in place at the time of or in advance of the main contract order being placed. Electrical installation includes the separate issue of connection to the national grid from the site substation either teeing into a nearest transmission line or through a purpose built

FIGURE 9 Blade erection at Corneen

FIGURE 10 Blade transportation to Corneen site

Table 12 Wind turbine installations – heavy-lift and transportation details

Capacity	MW	2500	1500	850
Height	m	100	100	75
Tower	m	60	65	49
Diameter	m	80	70	52
Weight	t	240	144	87
Tower	t	123	81	50
Nacelle	t	117	63	37
Tower Units	no.	3	3	2
Tower	t-m	43t-14m 48t-20m	36t-20m 26t-20m	20t-23m 30t-24m

dedicated line to an ESB substation. The on-site substation generally includes an outdoor electrical compound with grid transformer and current and voltage transformer units and overhead mast. It also includes an electrical building housing switchgear, grid protection and metering equipment. On site underground cables link the substation to the wind turbines, adjacent to each of which a unit transformer is housed. Detailed planning to ensure successful co-ordination and the installation of electrical equipment of the turbine supplier, the electrical subcontractor and the connection to the National Grid is essential and is the key to delivering the project on schedule. Establishing wayleaves on the route for overhead line connections to the national grid is equally important and due time must be given for this process.

Connection to the grid is the major milestone in any wind farm schedule and following this the on-site substation is energised. Commission of each of the wind turbines will follow on the energising of the unit transformers associated with each turbine. On large windfarms with many turbines it is usual practice to divide the turbines into a number of electrical loops to optimise both cable size and ensure partial completion of the project, if required.

2.9 Commissioning

The successful commissioning of a wind farm project, including a 240-hour reliability run, will lead into the operation phase. Due consideration must be given to the completion of all the works under the planning conditions. Monitoring of the project, as required, is then initiated. It is the responsibility of the developers, owners and operators to ensure the satisfactory operation throughout its lifetime. Unlike conditions imposed on other industrial developments, wind farm owners are obliged to remove all the turbines and return the site as closely as practicable to its original state at the end of its design life or should the project cease to

produce electricity for a specified period. Where the residual value of turbines and balance of plant is insufficient to cover the costs of this eventuality, responsible owners should set aside funds during the life of the project to cover decommissioning costs.

3 Economics of wind energy projects

The current cost of Irish windfarm installation is in the region of €1050 to €1150 per kilowatt installed, depending on the location, ground conditions and proximity to the national grid network – this amount excludes the preparations associated with and submission of a planning application and grid connection. A typical breakdown of these costs would show the following percentages for the main elements of the installation:

Turbine Supply	60%–75%
Civil Subcontract	10%–12%
Electrical Subcontract	8%–10%
Engineering	3%–5%

The cost of building and operating wind turbines has fallen dramatically in the last 20 years. In Denmark the cost of wind energy fell by two thirds in the period 1981 to 1995. In an experimental exercise undertaken by the ESB in the 1980s it was concluded that at a cost of 11p/kWh (14 Cent) it was not economical to make major investments in a wind power generation programme. In a recent AER competition this figure has now fallen to 3.8p/kWh (4.7 cent) - this reflecting that already experienced in Europe.

The revised Government programme for renewable energy targets a 13% level of electricity generation by 2010 from wind resources. This represents an increase from the current level of 125MW to 1250MW. An investment of 1125 million Euro will be required to achieve this target. The wind energy industry employs many thousands in Europe and it is estimated that each 1 MW of

installed capacity creates jobs for 20 people. The successful completion of the Irish target to 2010 would therefore create over 20,000 jobs. It is estimated that 24 man months of construction and installation work will arise for each 1 MW installed thus creating 2250 man-years of employment in Ireland.

4 Acknowledgements

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5 References

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FIGURE 11 The future...?